

Trends in unauthorised absences of children with special and additional needs in specialised care

Keywords: child and youth protection, special needs, additional needs, unauthorised absence

Abstract

Unauthorised absence poses a significant risk for children with special and/or additional needs who are placed in foster care or residential homes after being removed from their families and entering the child protection system. Due to their condition and heightened need for assistance, leaving their designated care environment compromises their safety. The lack of necessary support, combined with additional risks, not only endangers their development but may also threaten their lives.

This research analyses available statistical data to focus on trends related to the situation and opportunities of children with special and additional needs. It is based on the principle, supported by resilience research conducted in Hungary from a child protection perspective, that a family-like environment is more conducive to fostering resilience. Due to resilience's multidimensional nature, it is essential to consider internal and external resources, including the child's physical condition, disabilities, and the environment in which they are raised.

The research outlines the characteristics of unauthorised absences among children with special and/or additional needs care, focusing on the type of care environment. By analysing data related to children with special and additional needs and examining the specifics of the regulatory framework, the study identifies key aspects and potential intervention points. These insights can contribute to developing care settings that provide tailored, damage-specific care aligned with the children's needs, thereby supporting the prevention of unauthorised absences.

1. Introduction

Numerous legal regulations define the foundations, frameworks, and content of the child protection system. Professional expertise is essential to ensure that assistance, interventions, and procedures carried out in children's interests are always professional and lawful.

The protection and safety of children are key priorities reflected in Hungarian legislation. Act LXIV of 1991 promulgated the Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted in New York on November 20, 1989. The Convention emphasises the respect and safeguarding of children's rights. Article 3 of the Convention highlights the importance of the child's best interests, which serve as the starting point for state involvement, regulation, and the implementation of necessary measures to provide the protection and care essential for their well-being.

The Fundamental Law of Hungary states that "every child has the right to the protection and care necessary for their proper physical, mental, and moral development" (Fundamental Law of Hungary, Article XVI, Section 1). It also declares that "Hungary protects children through specific measures" (Fundamental Law of Hungary, Article XV, Section 5).

The 1997 Act XXXI on the Protection of Children and Guardianship Administration (hereinafter referred to as the Child Protection Act) elaborates on children's rights, ensuring their enforcement

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through the provisions outlined in the law (via benefits, services, and measures) as part of the child protection system. The child protection service operates based on the professional tasks and operational requirements specified in Decree 15/1998 (IV. 30.) on the personal care provided by child welfare and child protection institutions and individuals (hereinafter referred to as the NM Decree), as well as additional laws, protocols, and regulatory documents.

The adoption of the "National Action Plan 2030 to Ensure the Guarantees of Children's Rights" as established by Government Decree 1202/2023 (V. 22.), is based on the Council Recommendation (EU) 2021/1004 of June 14, 2021, on the European Child Guarantee. The recommendation's primary objectives include preventing and combating social exclusion, enforcing children's rights, fighting child poverty, and promoting equal opportunities by ensuring access to essential services for children in need.

The public's openness to topics and issues related to children also extends to child protection. This professional field garners varying levels of societal interest, influenced by diverse values and priorities. On April 3, 2022, a national referendum on issues affecting children saw 5.6 million people cast votes (3.9 million valid and 1.7 million invalid), while 2.58 million did not participate.

The 2023 Children's Rights Report, published by the Hintalovon Foundation for Children's Rights, presents findings from a study conducted by ZRI Závecz Research Market and Social Research Institute. This research, based on a representative sample of 1,000 individuals surveyed in person, identified the prioritisation of tasks in child protection based on options provided by the researchers. Among the respondents, 63.5% identified combating child abuse as the most critical task, followed by caring for children without parents (55.6%) and fighting child poverty (55.2%). Additionally, 43.6% of respondents highlighted caring for children removed from their families as one of the most crucial responsibilities (Children's Rights Report 2023).

Child protection is a topic that (due to some degree of involvement and/or interest) also invites opinions from the general public. While the widespread use of the term "child protection" and the associated messages in contemporary news channels and media platforms undeniably highlight the topic's relevance, it is essential to emphasise that the primary goal of this research, the problem analysis, and the conclusions drawn in this study is to ensure that professional solutions are prioritised in practice during professional work in the field.

The study is based on the principle, supported by child protection-focused resilience research conducted in Hungary, that becoming resilient is facilitated by a family-like environment (Rácz, 2012; Homoki, 2014b; Homoki & Czinderi, 2015; V. Gönczi, 2017; Bogács, 2021). Due to the multidimensional nature of resilience (Homoki, 2014a; Máté, 2015; Homoki et al., 2016), when identifying internal and external resources, the child's physical condition, disabilities, and the environment in which they are raised, whether foster care, a children's home, or a residential home must not be overlooked (Rácz, 2012; V. Gönczi & Gortka-Rákó, 2012).

The study focuses on children with special and/or additional needs, exploring the patterns of unauthorised absences. What might be the underlying motivations for escaping from care settings? Where and how can emotional security and damage-specific care that meets the children's needs be best ensured for those living in specialised care? What methodological considerations should be taken into account to assist these children effectively?

In outlining the trends and characteristics related to children with special and/or additional needs and unauthorised absences, the identification and analysis of problems and focal points aim to support the decision-making necessary to enforce children's rights and ensure the child's paramount interests.

2. Research Methodology

The primary method used in this research is the secondary analysis of statistical data related to children with special and additional needs care and their situations. Since significant legal changes in child protection professional care and foster care services took effect in 2014, the temporal scope of the research is defined from this point onwards. Comparing data that includes elemental distributions and national trends with literature, previous studies, and legal regulations and conducting the problem-specific analysis can help gain a deeper understanding of the patterns and correlations behind the data.

In the research, we sought data that indicates the presence of an environment providing the emotional security necessary for the children's development. We examined the number of foster parents, including those specialising in caring for children with special and additional needs, as well as the number of children placed with them. This data was compared with the number of children living in children's homes, specifically in homes for special and additional needs children and their age, based on the Hungarian Central Statistical Office's (KSH) Social Statistical Yearbooks data. The data on unauthorised absences also provides insight into how children in specialised care relate to their care settings, representing one of the research's key issues.

According to our hypothesis, in the case of children requiring special and/or additional needs care, the number of unauthorised absences is lower, and the trends are more favourable when placed with foster parents, compared to children placed in children's homes, particularly in special or additional children's homes.

3. Description of the Research

3.1. Key Concepts of the Research

3.1.1. Children with Special and/or Additional Needs in Specialized Care

When the Child Protection Act was first enacted, developmental characteristics that warranted special treatment were already recognised. However, the lack of differentiation in terms of the target group and the institutions providing care is well reflected in the text of the legislation as it was published at the time. The provisions for children requiring significant assistance and placed in specialised care were as follows: "In the case of home-based care, special care must be provided for children with disabilities, adaptation, behavioural or learning disorders, as well as children with specific needs due to their age" (Child Protection Act, Section 53 (2)).

"An additional needs care provider in a children's home or an additional needs group within a children's home provides care, socialisation, resocialisation, habilitation, and rehabilitation for children who are temporarily placed, who are in short- or long-term care, who are chronically ill,

disabled, struggle with integration, behaviour or learning disorders, suffer from addiction, or require special care due to their age" (Child Protection Act, Section 58 (1), official version).

The gap was recognised, and there was also a methodological need for the development of a more differentiated care system: "Currently, we only sense the demands of children and young people with additional needs, but we are not yet able to articulate them precisely, and as a result, a unified typology has not been developed. There is no established methodology for these homes. In many places, there are no additional needs care children's homes, so the placement of children with additional needs is incidental, and they are often moved from one home to another without receiving the appropriate assistance and care" (Negrea & Büki, 1999, p. 28).

In November 1999, a comprehensive questionnaire-based survey was conducted covering the entire field of additional needs care, which aimed to collect data on the number of children. Researchers also sought written interpretations of additional needs from child protection professionals (foster care advisors and staff members of children's homes and residential homes). Additionally, they asked for descriptions of these children's problems and, where applicable, the successful problem-solving strategies employed (Domszky et al., 2000). The data collected served as the foundation for developing methodological recommendations for the care and upbringing of children with additional needs in child protection services.

The scope of the target group of children with special and/or additional needs was more precisely defined by Section 37 (1) of Act IX of 2002, amending the 1997 Act XXXI on child protection and guardianship administration. The legal framework included special needs children's homes and additional needs care children's homes as care facilities. This modification forms the basis of the current applicable regulations (Child Protection Act, Section 53), which stipulate that special care must be provided for children who are chronically ill, disabled, or under the age of three. Additional needs care must be provided for children exhibiting severe psychological symptoms, severe dissocial behaviours, children using psychoactive substances, and children who have potentially become victims of human trafficking.² Both special and additional care must be provided simultaneously for children with dual needs.

The additional needs care children's homes, additional needs care groups in children's homes, or children's homes for children with additional and dual needs provide care, socialisation, resocialisation, as well as habilitation and rehabilitation (Child Protection Act, Section 58 (1)). In addition to the regional institutions, there are five central additional needs care children's homes operating in Hungary, which are national intake institutions; for girls in Esztergom and Rákospalota, and for boys in Zalaegerszeg, Kalocsa, and Fót. Children can be placed in care facilities that provide care according to their additional needs based on the professional opinion and recommendation of the county, metropolitan, or national child protection expert committees (Child Protection Act, Section 82).

² The group of children recognized as having special needs under the Child Protection Act was expanded by Section 1 of Act V of 2020 on the Amendment of Certain Laws to Combat the Exploitation of Victims of Human Trafficking. This includes children who violate the prohibition on offering sexual services, as defined by the law on combating organized crime and certain related phenomena, and on amendments to related laws (hereinafter referred to as: children presumed to be victims of human trafficking).

Under the current regulations, the care, treatment, habilitation, and rehabilitation of children requiring special care and those with dual needs are provided by special children's homes, children's homes, or children's home groups established for this purpose, according to Section 58 (6) of the Child Protection Act.³ This is provided as long as the child's placement in foster care is not feasible. The child's condition does not warrant placement in a facility under the Social Administration and Social Services Act of 1993 (Act No. III of 1993, hereafter referred to as the Social Act) for persons with disabilities or psychiatric patients, or if placement is not possible due to a lack of available space.

As stipulated in Act CXC of 2011 on Public Education, determining a child's special care needs requires the opinion of an expert committee, including a diagnosis of disability. This expert opinion is necessary to assess the child's specific needs and ensure appropriate care and support are provided. Therefore, the term "special need" specified in the Child Protection Act is not identical to the terms "special educational needs" or "children with difficulties in integration, learning, or behaviour" as defined in the Public Education Act. Each term carries distinct implications and serves different legal and practical frameworks for addressing children's needs.

According to Section 4, Paragraph 13 of the Public Education Act, the category of "children and students requiring special attention" includes: on the one hand, those "requiring special treatment" (within this, those with "special educational needs," those "struggling with integration, learning, or behavioral difficulties," and exceptionally gifted students); on the other hand, children and students considered disadvantaged or multiply disadvantaged under the Child Protection Act; and, thirdly, children and students undergoing long-term medical treatment.

Furthermore, Section 4(3) defines "children with difficulties in integration, learning, or behaviour as those requiring special treatment, who—based on the expert opinion of a specialist committee—significantly underperform relative to their age, experience difficulties with social relationships, and struggle with learning or behavioural regulation, their integration into communities and their personal development are hindered or show unique tendencies, but they are not classified as having special educational needs."

Among the possible definitions and theoretical approaches to the concepts of special and additional needs (e.g., diagnostic, scientific, legislative), the normative (legal) approach is justified for use in the present study based on the above. This is because belonging to categories established by legislation provides the legal basis for the provision of need-specific services (Büki & Szollár, 2004).

Eligibility for the conceptualisation includes the omission of children from the categories of special and/or additional needs who lack an expert opinion because they have not undergone evaluation by

³ Section 43 of Act IX of 2002 originally inserted the provision regarding the placement of children with special needs into Section 58 (4) of the Child Protection Act. This section (58) was structurally changed and its content slightly modified by Section 14 of Act CCV of 2013 on the amendment of Act XXXI of 1997 on the Protection of Children and Guardianship Administration and certain related acts concerning the transformation of foster care and special care. The amendment came into effect on July 1, 2014, at which point the content of Section 58 (4) was moved to Section 58 (6).

The content of Section 58 (6) of the Child Protection Act was supplemented with provisions on supported housing, thanks to Section 61 (1) a) of Act CXXVI of 2019 on the Amendment of Certain Laws Related to the Family Protection Action Plan.

a specialist committee. It may occur due to reasons such as unauthorised absences or other circumstances, even though an assessment would be justified in their case.

A critical issue for children with special and/or additional needs arises when they reach adulthood, as the classification of special needs or additional needs ceases to apply. While the needs themselves, as well as any diagnosed disabilities or illnesses, do not disappear, the services and enhanced care tailored to these needs are no longer available.

Upon reaching adulthood, young individuals who previously received special or additional care as minors are limited to the placement options accessible to peers with standard needs who request aftercare or those provided under the Social Welfare Act in facilities offering personal care services. However, Section 58(2) of the Child Protection Act allows for continued care beyond the age of 18 if it is necessary to meet the young person's specific needs, support their therapeutic requirements, or enable the completion of their studies. After turning 18, access to aftercare services depends on the young adult's personal request. This care can be provided in licensed facilities such as additional needs care children's homes, additional needs care residential homes, or additional needs care groups within children's homes.

Based on the above reasoning, the research considers children to have special and/or additional needs if they possess an expert committee's official assessment attesting to these needs. This assessment serves as a decisive factor for their placement within the child protection system. Consequently, these children are the ones accounted for in statistical data reporting.

3.1.2. Unauthorized Absence (Escape)

The unauthorised departure of children from their care settings represents a significant issue, as minors without supervision or care are at risk of harm. The complex problem of escapes is not new to the field of child protection services; however, it remains one of the most challenging areas to address. The investigation documented in OBH 550/1998 criticised the lack of effective measures to prevent such incidents (Bede et al., 2010).

Bogács & Hüse (2015) emphasise that children who are missing from care due to unauthorised departures require heightened attention because their risk factors significantly exceed the usual risks encountered in child protection. This is particularly true for the most vulnerable groups, including children with special and/or additional needs. The National Action Plan 2030 to Ensure the Guarantees of Children's Rights, also underscores this issue, identifying children removed from their families—especially girls and those with disabilities, substance use issues or histories of abuse—as a particularly endangered group. These factors, often underlying their special or additional needs, make them highly susceptible to becoming victims of crimes such as abuse, human trafficking, and child prostitution. In cases of unauthorised departures, there is also a significant risk that these children may become perpetrators of crimes themselves. Bogács (2018) identifies unauthorised absences as a critical area for joint action between child welfare services and child protection institutions, highlighting the importance of collaborative intervention strategies in mitigating these risks.

The NM regulation Section 86 contains provisions regarding runaways. A child is considered to have left without permission if they leave their place of care without authorisation or fail to return by the designated time.

When an unauthorised departure occurs, the care provider is responsible for immediately notifying the child protection guardian and, in cooperation with them, attempting to locate the child's whereabouts. Additionally, if the runaway child is under 14 years old or is unable to care for themselves due to illness or disability, the relevant police authority must be contacted without delay. (In other cases, this notification must occur within 24 hours.)

This notification is typically made using a dedicated form that includes the child's personal data, a detailed physical description, identifying features (e.g. scar, tattoo, birthmark, speech fault, pregnancy), the clothing worn at the time of departure, the circumstances of the departure, possible locations where the child might be found, and a photo that can help identify the child.

The care provider must also inform the child's parents or other legal representatives. This measure facilitates the possibility that if the child seeks refuge with their parents, the parents can inform the children's home or foster parent to help return the child safely.

If the child who left without permission is found by the care provider or returns voluntarily to the place of care, the care provider must immediately, but no later than within 24 hours, notify the relevant police authority, the parent, and the child protection guardian. If the child is found by the police, the parent, other legal representatives, and the child protection guardian must also be informed.

Once the child who left without permission returns to their place of care, an individual interview should be conducted with the child, involving the child protection guardian, to uncover the reasons and circumstances of their departure, as well as what happened during their absence, where they stayed, and their sources of livelihood. The interview must be documented in writing, including the key points of the conversation, and the necessary measures should be taken based on the findings.

The Child Protection Act lists the duties of child protection guardians, including the responsibility to "if it is known where the child has gone, return the child to the care place in case of unauthorised departure from the care place; otherwise, take the necessary steps to locate the child" (Child Protection Act, Section 86, Subsection (1), Point g).

In the context of child protection institutions operating within specialized care, procedural guidelines are established by the providers. The reporting obligations required in the event of unauthorized absence are detailed in the regulations concerning extraordinary events. According to the provider's regulations, every institution offering specialized care must develop its own internal policy. This policy must include procedures to be followed in cases of unauthorized absence, specifying tasks, responsibilities, authorities, and deadlines.

In state-maintained child protection institutions, Regulation 9/2022 (IX. 28.) of the Directorate-General for Social and Child Protection defines the scope of extraordinary events and the measures to be taken in such cases. According to Section 2 Subsection (5) b) to d) of the document, the unauthorised absence of a child under the age of 14 from a child protection institution, the unauthorised absence of a child in an additional needs care central children's home, and the unauthorised absence of at least three children aged 14 or over from a child protection institution, if they do not return to their place of care within 24 hours, are considered other exceptional occurrences. In these cases, the head of the institution is obliged (in addition to any official investigation) to conduct an internal investigation to identify the causes of the incident and to establish responsibility, which "must include whether there was a precedent for the incident, what

measures have been taken or are planned to be taken to deal with it, and how similar situations can be prevented. The investigation should objectively examine how mandatory professional standards were implemented in relation to the event, how legal regulations, internal policies, and job descriptions were adhered to, and whether any negligence or error occurred in the institution's operations (Regulation 9/2022 Section 5, Subsections (1)-(2)).

According to the Regulation on the Procedure for Reporting and Handling of Incidents in the Institutional System of the St. Agota Child Protection Service, other incidents are "the unauthorised absence of a child under the age of 14 from a care place (foster care, children's home, residential home) operated by the Institution, and the unauthorised absence of 5 or more children over the age of 14 in a care place operated by the Institution." (St. Agostia Principal Regulation No. 12-6/2022, point III.2.4). This Regulation mentions using a secure isolation unit for children with special needs as an exceptional occurrence. However, it does not lay down different rules for unauthorised absences for both special and additional needs children. The Service Provider operates both a special needs children's home and an additional needs care residential home in accordance with the Service Provider's Organisational and Operational Rules No. 12-6/2024.

3.2. Children with Special and Exceptional Care Needs in the Child Protection System as Reflected in Statistical Data

According to legislative changes introduced in 2014, children under the age of 12 who have been removed from their families and placed into the child protection system should, as far as possible, receive home-like care from foster parents. Efforts must also be made to ensure that children removed from their families do not grow up in institutional environments. However, situations may arise where institutional placement serves the child's best interests. Such cases may include situations where the child has a chronic illness or severe disability or where the need arises to accommodate large sibling groups together.

Research on children living in the child protection system (aligned with resilience studies from a child protection perspective) emphasises the critical importance of family-like care during the early years of life, particularly for children under the age of three (Herczog, 2001; Kardos, 2001; V. Gönczi, 2002, 2017).

1. Table: The Proportion of Foster Placements for Minors in Specialized Child Protection Care between 2014-2020

Year	Number of Minors Receiving Specialized Child Protection Care	Number of Those Placed with Foster Parents	%
2014	20 135	12 832	63,7
2015	20 271	12 948	63,9
2016	20 551	13 502	65,7
2017	20 948	14 039	67
2018	21 210	14 493	68,3
2019	20 876	14 357	68,8
2020	20 743	14 562	70,2

Source: from Central Social Office Social Statistics Yearbook (2014-2020) own edition, 2024.

During the period under review, an increasing proportion of children removed from their families were placed in foster care. According to the National Action Plan 2030 to Ensure the Guarantees of Children's Rights, which includes the total number of minors and young adults in specialised child protection care, 69.1% of all children in care (23 327) were in foster care on 31 December 2021. This rate was higher for children under 12 years old, at 87.4%. The document confirms that the government's priority policy is to maintain, improve and support the proportion of children in foster care in terms of places.

Regarding children in specialised childcare, while the number and proportion of children placed in special and additional needs care children's homes decreased slightly after 2014, the number of children placed in special foster care and additional needs foster care also increased, especially in 2019 and 2020.

2. Table: Comparative Data on Placement Types and Child Needs for the Years 2014-2020

Number of Minors Placed in Children's Homes and with Foster Parents (Temporary and Foster Care)	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Number of Minors Living in General Children's Homes and Apartment Homes	4750	4458	4643	4939	4778	4585	4376
Number of Minors Living in Additional needs Care Children's Homes and Apartment Homes	445	452	440	426	448	448	411
Number of Minors Living in Special needs care Children's Homes and Apartment Homes	1296	1237	1204	1099	1103	1119	1069
Number of Minors Living with Foster Parents (no special needs or additional needs care)	10264	10514	10635	11163	11475	10699	10473
Number of Minors Living with foster parents who provide special needs care	2317	2405	2821	2720	2682	3575	4086
Number of Minors Living with foster parents who provide additional needs care	17	19	11	7	20	73	70

Source: from Central Social Office Social Statistics Yearbook (2014-2020) own edition, 2024.

During the observed period, the majority of children with special needs, due to their age, lived with foster parents. The increase in the number of infants entering the child protection system paralleled the rise in young children placed with foster families.

In 2020, 70% of children in the child protection system lived with foster parents, while 30% resided in children's homes. Of the children placed in children's homes, 6% had additional needs, compared to only 0.5% of those living with foster parents.

The placement of severely disabled and/or chronically ill young children requiring intensive care with foster parents poses a significant challenge. This difficulty arises due to the lack of adequate preparation among foster parents and the shortage of necessary personal and material resources (Gyarmati et al., 2018; Czibere et al., 2021). For foster parents caring for children with special, additional, and dual needs, specialised selection, preparation, and higher financial support are

recommended to meet the child’s needs fully. Additional financial investment may also be required for home furnishings and the acquisition of assistive devices (Báló et al., 2015).

3. Table: Breakdown of children aged 0-3 in child protection care by placement from 2014 to 2020

Number of Minors in Child Protection Care (Temporary and Long-term Care)	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Number of Children Aged 0-3 Years	2874	2834	3117	3277	3464	3479	3457
Number of 0-3-Year-Olds Living in Children's Homes	363	348	357	381	361	351	313
Number of 0-3-Year-Olds Living with Foster Parents	2477	2673	2884	3074	2970	3062	3145

Source: from Central Social Office Social Statistics Yearbook (2014-2020) own edition, 2024.

The data support the increase in capacity for children with special needs, which contributes to this trend (the number of special foster parents has increased by 1.5 times). However, not all children with special needs have been placed with a special needs foster parent.

However, the circumstances do not justify a higher number of placements with additional needs foster parents, as the number of additional needs foster parents has not changed as much as the number of children placed with them.

Negrea-Büki (1999) describes the placement of children and young people with additional needs in residential care as a necessary evil, which is justified when adoption and foster care are not feasible. Büki (2015) stresses that the "empty place principle" should not prevail, but that children who are singled out from their families should be placed in the most appropriate care placement.

The report of the Commissioner for Fundamental Rights in case AJB-276/2023 records that from 1 January 2021, the additional payment to foster parents for a child with special, additional or dual needs placed with them has increased (from 5% to 7% of the minimum wage).

4. Table: Comparative Data on Foster Parent Status and Child Needs from 2014 to 2020

Number of Minors Placed in Children's Homes and with Foster Parents (Temporary and Foster Care)	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Number of Foster Parents providing special needs care	959	1142	882	1055	1224	1135	1413
Number of Minors Living with Foster Parents providing special needs care	2317	2405	2821	2720	2682	3575	4086
Number of Foster Parents providing additional needs care	10	8	15	15	14	15	14
Number of Minors Living with Foster Parents providing additional needs care	17	19	11	7	20	73	70

Source: from Central Social Office Social Statistics Yearbook (2014-2020) own edition, 2024.

The number of fostered minors per additional needs foster carer is more than two each year, but the figure of 70-73 children living with 14-15 additional needs foster carers raises further questions, as placing more children with severe mental health, psychiatric, psychosocial issues or psychoactive substance use problems in one foster home does not seem to be the optimal solution. It is possible

that children with additional needs are not living in additional needs foster care or that there is another explanation: children with additional needs are being sent to correctional institution or prisons. In these cases, although the place of care may be the foster parent, the actual care of the juveniles is provided elsewhere, and therefore, more than one child may be placed with a foster parent at the same time. Frequent changes in care placement are also a known phenomenon in the lives of children with additional needs (Büki, 2023a), meaning that the figures may also indicate that so many children have turned to additional needs foster care in a year. If this is the relevant explanation, it could also mean that it was decided in a very short period that the placement was unsuccessful.

According to the National Action Plan 2030 to Ensure the Guarantees of Children's Rights, around 1% of children in child protection have a serious psychiatric condition. Their upbringing is a significant challenge for a care system with average conditions, and they are therefore placed in centralised additional needs care children's homes. The purpose of these institutions is to provide care and appropriate therapy for these children with additional needs and severe conditions, to ensure that their needs are met and to prevent or reduce their deterioration. The document states that these institutions' development and expanding their services are significant tasks.

The possibility of establishing various types and functions of child protection care institutions has long been discussed. One such concept is the "therapeutic" children's home, envisioned as a facility in a sanatorium-like setting designed to accommodate 6-8 children. Ideally, this type of home would be situated in an environment conducive to organising appropriate recreational activities. It has been proposed primarily for children under child protection care who suffer from psychiatric disorders. The therapeutic children's home would employ healthcare professionals and provide various therapies and activities, along with educational and pedagogical programs and techniques suited to the additional needs care children's homes.

Another proposed concept is the "intensive occupational children's home," which is based on addressing the social and psychological problems of children classified as "deviant," at risk of antisocial behaviour, and/or self- or socially harmful. (Negrea-Büki, 1999:35).

The issue of proper placement and differentiation in the tools and organisation of institutional care has been a longstanding challenge and objective in the field of child protection care. This approach rests on the assumption that "there are social situations from which the children's home network is practically unable to handle the entrants (...). Experience shows that during this process, not only do the problems existing at the time of removal from the family remain unresolved, but further severe harms exacerbate integration difficulties, tragically reducing the chances of later corrective treatment." (B. Aczél, 1985:119)

For children with severe mental health symptoms and/or dual needs, institutional placements that can provide enhanced psychiatric support, which are still lacking in the Hungarian care system, could also be justified. More medical, child psychiatric support could be needed in the additional needs care home or central additional needs care home settings for children with severe psychiatric problems, in addition to education based on experiential teaching. Providing care for a target group based on the leading symptoms could facilitate the development of a safe environment and attitudes conducive to children's development.

The data also confirm that the "special need care" defined in the Child Protection Act and the "special educational need" outlined in the Public Education Act do not align, and there is a lack of coherence between the two legal sources. For infants and young children categorised as having special care needs due to their age, it is uncommon for them to come under the purview of expert committees where their special educational needs might be diagnosed. Within the child protection care system, both in children's homes and with foster parents, some individuals are not classified as having special needs care but require additional support due to their special educational needs. Furthermore, there are children with special needs care (such as those under the age of three living in children's homes) who are not placed in special needs children's homes.

5. Table: The types of placements of the SEN minors

Number of minors	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Number of SEN minors placed in children's home (temporary and foster care)	1807	1794	1759	1812	1806	1781	1719
Number of minors living in Special needs children's homes and apartment	1296	1237	1204	1099	1103	1119	1069
Number of children under 3 years of age living in Children's homes	363	348	357	381	361	351	313
Number of SEN minors living with foster parents (temporary and foster care)	2038	2025	2345	2469	2601	2664	2748
Number of minors living with foster parents providing special needs care	2317	2405	2821	2720	2682	3575	4086
Number of children under 3 years of age living with foster parents	2477	2673	2884	3074	2970	3062	3145

Source: from Central Social Office Social Statistics Yearbook (2014-2020) own edition, 2024.

The data on unauthorised absences may reflect the attitudes of children living in professional care toward their placement, which formed the primary focus of the research.

6. Table: Unauthorized leave incidents between 2014 and 2020

Number of escape incidents	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Number of minors living in general children's homes and residential homes	4750	4458	4643	4939	4778	4585	4376
Number of unauthorised leave incidents from general children's homes and residential homes	17331	20143	20804	14961	14209	15881	20455
Number of minors living in additional needs care children's homes and residential homes	445	452	440	426	448	448	411
Number of unauthorised leave incidents from additional needs care children's homes and residential homes	3163	4884	3864	2421	2159	1785	1756
Number of minors living in special care	1296	1237	1204	1099	1103	1119	1069

children's homes and residential homes							
Number of unauthorised leave incidents from special needs care children's homes and residential homes	2134	2817	2378	1430	1956	1703	1993
Total number of minors living with foster parents	12598	12938	13467	13890	14177	14347	14629
Number of unauthorised leave incidents from foster parents	434	483	456	314	365	349	361

Source: from Central Social Office Social Statistics Yearbook (2014-2020) own edition, 2024.

The data indicates that, in many cases, a child leaves an institution without permission multiple times, as the number of incidents far exceeds the number of children in care.

Based on Table 6, it is evident that children placed with foster parents exhibit significantly lower rates of unauthorised absences compared to those in children's homes. This substantial difference may partly stem from the children's age and also point to the effectiveness of matching placements. Creating an environment that provides physical and emotional security is paramount for children, as their ability to cope with life's challenges, both as children and later as adults, is greatly enhanced when this security is present during childhood (Vekerdy, 2024). Logic suggests that where a child feels safe, they are less likely to run away, adapt better, and thus foster stronger trust and relationships with their foster parents. However, if collaboration fails for some reason, the child may be moved to a new placement (Kálmánchey, 2001). This dynamic helps explain why the number of unauthorised absences remains low in foster care while children's homes may concentrate on those with integration or behavioural difficulties, severe attachment traumas, or special, additional, or dual needs. These children have often experienced multiple placements in their short lives.

Bede (et al. 2010) identified the issue of unauthorised absences as particularly severe in institutions providing additional needs care. In contrast, such incidents were not characteristic of children's homes established for age-related or health-related reasons, nor in institutions caring for children with disabilities. Rákó (2014), in a questionnaire-based study conducted among children and young people aged 13–25 living in child protection institutions in Hajdú-Bihar County, found that the number of unauthorised absences was lower in residential homes than among those living in children's homes.

Unauthorised absences are a multifactorial phenomenon that can arise due to the complex interplay of various factors (Bede et al., 2010). "Escape is a symptom with complex causes behind it" (Varga, n.d.). Central statistical data on these causes is unavailable, and empirical research results are scarce, so we primarily rely on analyses and sources published in the professional literature.

The report of the Commissioner for Fundamental Rights in case AJB-1140/2012 examined the issue of children's disappearances (wandering, escaping). According to its findings, children aged 14 and over, particularly girls who live in child protection care facilities, are the most affected. Many of them reside in institutions providing additional needs care, and during escapes, they typically go to their parents, other relatives, friends, or, in the case of girls over 14, often to their boyfriends. This leads to an increased possibility of unwanted, unplanned pregnancy with its every consequences. It is common for a child to leave the institution without permission multiple times, and there are

instances where someone is continuously on the run, even spending no time at the children's home at all (Győrffy, 2012).

Early childhood adversities in children's medical histories, children's health and current mental health, family and friendships, attachment mechanisms, socialisation influences, patterns, socio-cultural background, life course events, and previous runaway behaviour may play a role in runaways. In care settings, these childhood influences can be nuanced by the built and social environment, such as the child's role in the group's daily experiences of success and failure (Bede et al., 2010). Thus, all the help, or lack of it, that can lead to their personal development, improvement of their condition, and development of their abilities can be important. In many cases, children who enter an additional needs care children's home have already been severely harmed, severely traumatised, sometimes criminalised, victims of prostitution, faces high expectations, and would need to adapt to different circumstances. As young children, many of them may have experienced changes in their care placement, which leave a lasting mark on their personality development and self-esteem (Büki, 2023a). Escaping from constraints and rules may be a method used as a crisis or conflict management strategy.

Bede (et al. 2010), using previous research based on a small sample of items available in manuscripts, concluded that the vast majority of unauthorised care leavers were adolescents aged between 14 and 17. Age was found to be more characteristic than gender. For almost half of the children, vagrancy was a relevant reason for admission, and they left without permission shortly after being placed in a children's home. Determining factors behind running away, according to the research, were family patterns, previous care placements, partner relationships, fun, casual relationships and offendings. In their study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with young people aged 12-18 living in children's homes in the capital and their guardians. The children mainly mentioned a lack of intimacy and feelings of closeness, as well as a lack of impulses and separation from family as motivations for running away.

Based on foreign studies, the motives for absconding can be divided into three groups. One is the longing for family ties, another is the need to control their own lives, which includes the desire for adventure and freedom, as well as the rejection of constraints, rules, and institutional circumstances, and the third is a coping strategy, a way of expressing emotions: escaping from problems, abandonment, feelings of helplessness, lack of stability (Varga, n.d., Czibere et al, n.d.).

In child protection, the harms suffered in childhood in the various care settings should be treated in the circumstances available. It is because it is well known from child psychology studies that the events of adolescence depend on how the 8-10-12 years preceding adolescence have passed (Vekerdy, 2019).

Research findings on the role of care placements vary somewhat. "In the case of unauthorised absences, the number of persistent runs of more than one month may indicate something about the retaining power of the care placement, but with varying relevance from child to child." (Demcsik et al, 2016:95)

Other research has found that the positive human environment of children's homes has a retaining power in many cases. (Czibere et al, n.d.) Researchers have found that the institution's accepting attitude and the programmes and experiences provided are more influential factors for runaways than children's regular or average needs (Bede et al., 2010). Most professionals in the child

protection system do not believe that the system provides adequate methodological tools (Rácz, 2022). This finding may also include the problem of runaways.

The interior design of an additional needs care children's home and the spatial and material conditions of the home can also play a role in how comfortable children feel in their living environment. The NM Decree (Section 124, 125) defines the accommodation conditions in children's homes and residential care homes. While a sense of home is important in creating emotional security for children in special children's homes, it is also relevant to avoid the acquisition and storage of objects and furniture that may be likely to cause harm to themselves or others by children with severe psychological and/or psychosocial symptoms. It is very difficult to strike this balance. Anger outbursts can cause damage to windows and furniture, which may need to be repaired or replaced regularly and, therefore, require a person to carry out maintenance work.

The majority of children in child protection services go to school, leave the children's home and return to it on a daily basis. In the central additional needs care children's homes, the condition of the children justifies a more closed environment. For the minors placed there, there is a possibility under Section 45 (5) of the Public Education Act to progress in an individual work schedule, which may be justified by their previous school failure (Büki, 2023a), as many of them are several years behind the age-appropriate grade level. They attend learning support sessions in the children's home, take class exams every six months, or study in the boarding school. These children must also be allowed to be outdoors without supervised activities, per Section 112(1)(f) of the NM Decree. Daily airing may also be an opportunity for unauthorised leave, especially if a low fence surrounds the yard of the children's home. In order to promote the education, development, therapy and social integration of children with additional needs, it is particularly necessary to organise experiential activities outside the institution. However, risk assessment is essential before participation, given the priority of children's safety. A complex system of motivation, feedback, assessment and reward developed in the children's home can also increase children's emotional security, self-esteem and self-confidence. However, all professionals must apply these principles consistently and keep them in the long term.

Children's emotional security can be fundamentally determined by the social environment in which they live. Children are placed in a children's home based on the professional opinion of the expert committees. According to Section 126(5) of the NM Decree, taken into account under Section 130, a maximum of 40 children in total, but no more than 8 children per group, may be placed in an additional needs care children's home, and no more than 8 children in an additional needs care residential home and in an additional needs care group in a children's home, with the proviso that only children of the same sex may be placed within each group. According to Section 5 (a), a maximum of 2 children with dual needs may be placed in a group except in the best interests of the children concerned. When a child with dual needs is placed in a group, the number of children in the group may be reduced, but the legislation does not give precise guidance on how much. What is important is the number of peers a child has to live with and the number of adults involved. Here again, foster care may be preferable. Children placed in an additional needs care children's home may have severe attachment trauma due to difficulties they have experienced in their lives. They may be in great need of personalised attention. Being in a fraternal community is not a sufficient reason a basis for them to form friendships; they can be rivals in the battle for attention rather than

supportive buddies. In adolescence, when peer group influences are strong, dominance struggles between children also emerge. These in-group dynamics can also be an essential component of children's emotional security, and if they can provide support and help, it can keep them within the children's home. However, interactions can also occur in ways that lead to each other running away.

Pursuant to Section 58 (3) and (4) of the Child Protection Act, the period of care of a child in an additional needs care children's home, additional needs care residential home, or additional needs care group of children's homes may not exceed two years in the same place of care, may exceed two years only in exceptional cases, for example, in order to complete the child's therapy, school year or participation in education, for a maximum of one year, or until the additional need is met extension is available. This arrangement makes it difficult to establish permanence, given the partners' frequent arrival and departure. This occurs when they experience adolescent identity problems in line with their age characteristics (Erikson, 2019; Vekerdy, 2019), and when the role of peer groups is prominent, it is important to develop friendships. Frequent changes in care placement and damage to the attachment to the family make it more difficult for these children to develop a natural support system (Büki, 2023a). Foreign studies have identified placement instability as one of the main risk factors behind runaways (Varga, n.d.)

The absence of family and the desire to have contact with family members or a romantic partner are also critical points in children's lives, and they can be motivating factors for running away. The role of the family can be crucial in preventing unauthorised absconding (Bede et al., 2010, Rácz-Sik, 2021). According to Section 75 (1) of the NM Regulation, a looked after child in residential care must be provided with family care in addition to complete care or, if this is not possible, with the facilitation of adoption. Children's homes no longer need a family care worker to coordinate contact with the family. However, it may be important to review the arrangements for contact with children, the realistic options, and to assist families in primary care in cooperation with child protection guardians, guardianship authorities and child welfare institutions (Büki, 2023a). Among the tasks of child welfare services, activities related to the families of children in care are often relegated to the background (Bogács et al., 2015).

The self-harming and public behaviour of children with severe psychological symptoms and/or severe psychosocial symptoms can lead to tantrums, conflicts, and situations that endanger the physical safety and lives of the children's peers and the professionals providing care, which also make it difficult for children to develop emotional security. The human resources and resources available for the prevention and adequate treatment of cases of abuse (peer abuse, offences of violence against public officials) appear to be inadequate. Annexe 1 of the NM Decree does not assign a police specialist to the additional needs care children's home, although this could be justified due to the aggressive behaviour of the residents. A relevant question is also what concept or model should be used for the treatment of delinquent, "morally handicapped" (Volentics, 2004) young people, and where (although this is an area of competence of the judiciary) is the borderline between the point where the young person is not sufficiently cared for in an additional needs care children's home and the point where placement in a correctional institution under Section 66/M of the Child Protection Act becomes necessary under Article 120 of Act C of 2012 on the Criminal Code (Büki, 2023b)? Professionals in children's homes should pay great attention to teaching children

conflict prevention and management techniques, as well as tension reduction. These are also practised during daily psychological support based on behavioural therapy.

The provision of human resources is a significant problem in all child protection institutions in the country. There is a high turnover of staff in child protection (Büki, 2023a) and a risk of burnout and fatigue. This problem may be particularly relevant in special and additional needs care children's homes due to the specificities of the target group served. Meeting the needs of those cared for in a special needs children's home requires increased workload and attention. Based on the professional staffing targets set out in Annex 1 to the NM Decree, it is not possible to provide parallel services in a group of children's homes on a continuous basis. The 2 educators, 1 child protection assistant, 2 child supervisors and (in an additional needs care children's home) 1 extra educator or child supervisor assigned to a group do not allow this. Due to the lack of other professionals (special needs teachers, psychologists), not all children in institutions for children under three with special needs receive the therapy they need (Gyarmati et al., 2018).

In order to prevent and adequately treat children in additional needs care children's homes from self-harm and, public danger, all kinds of abuse, and to guarantee the severity of the condition of the children in additional needs care children's homes, the amount of care tasks and basic security of care, it would be necessary to define a minimum number of professionals in these institutions to allow for parallel services (continuously, but in any case during the day). For professionals, the constant focused attention on preventing unauthorised absences and conflicts is an increased workload. Therefore, it would be necessary to provide supervision everywhere, which could also help to deal with similar cases (Miklósi, 2015).

The addiction of children who use psychoactive substances can be a constant strong inner urge to run away and get drugs. Smoking and occasionally alcohol consumption may also be harmful habits in their medical history (Murányi, n.d.; Murányi, 2000), and they may not have the opportunity to do so within the walls of the children's home.

The period of unauthorised leave is also particularly problematic for children with additional needs because children with psychiatric illnesses have a fundamental need to be provided with the medication prescribed for them. If they are using drugs or other mind-altering substances during the period of absconding, this, together with the absence of medication, can lead to a severe deterioration in their condition. The OBH investigation report No 550/1998 interpreted the unresolved situation of absconding and drug use as a serious problem. This situation threatened the rights enshrined in the Constitution in force at the time.

If in the additional needs children's home, spending pocket money is part of the educational tasks in order to learn the value, allocation and management of money, and if the planning and implementation of the purchase are done together with the professionals, and the safe storage of the money is essential, then the children cannot take money with them even when they go out without permission. Thus, they may also commit crimes in order to obtain tobacco or drugs or be victims of crime, e.g. through child prostitution. According to the National Action Plan 2030 to Ensure the Guarantees of Children's Rights, 242 out of 3407 children who escaped from child protection in 2020 committed crimes, mainly against property.

The children's current state of health, physical and mental well-being and the measures taken to ensure this can also play an important role in how they perceive their situation in the children's

home. A sense of balance and emotional security can help to prevent runaways. There are, therefore, a number of points to be considered in relation to the health care and medication of children in additional needs care children's homes. Annex 1 to the NM Decree, which sets out the professional staffing guidelines and minimum staffing standards for personal care services for children and child protection, does not assign a nurse to the additional needs children's home. The professionals working with the child cannot oblige the child to take the medication, nor can they use coercive measures in the case of opposition. However, if the pharmacotherapy becomes irregular, the effectiveness of the therapy is reduced, which can also be seen in the child's emotional state and behaviour.

Based on the above-mentioned aspects, it may be appropriate to develop institutions that could be designed explicitly as therapeutic institutions for adolescent psychiatric patients and psychoactive substance users, providing specific care for the relevant target group. There would also be a need to provide a backup health facility for child psychiatric care for those in additional needs care children's homes.

The role of psychiatric care in the lives of children with additional needs would be key in the diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation plan, especially for those with severe psychiatric symptoms or who use psychoactive substances (Lánczi, 2014).

4. Summary and Conclusions

Statistical data on children with special and additional care needs and their circumstances indicate that between 2014 and 2020, an increasing proportion of children removed from their families were placed with foster parents. In cases of placement with foster families, the number of unauthorised absences is lower, and the trends are more favourable compared to children living in children's homes, special needs children's homes, or additional needs care children's homes. Thus, the research hypothesis has been confirmed.

By comparing legislation, statistical data, academic literature, and the results of previous studies, it becomes evident that many factors can contribute to absconding from care placements. Key factors include the child's previous life history, family background, personality state, needs, and the adequacy of the care placement provided. Establishing emotional security and ensuring care that meets the children's needs requires considering numerous methodological aspects.

In cases where children are removed from their families, accurately determining their needs is a crucial factor for their placement. Based on the enforcement of children's rights and considering their best interests, it is relevant from both a legal and professional perspective to ensure that they are placed in a care setting that can provide the most appropriate, damage-specific care, upbringing, and development.

"We cannot ignore the fact that, in certain cases, families and institutions themselves contribute to the development of additional needs, and often, the dysfunctional families and institutions contribute to the perpetuation of these problems" (Negrea-Büki, 1999, p. 29). This underscores the importance of regional child protection professional services. Their role is to make recommendations regarding the care setting that provides home-like care for the child. Furthermore, upon the request of the guardianship authority, they conduct personality assessments

of the child, prepare a professional opinion, and develop placement recommendations as well as the child's individual placement plan (Child Protection Act, Section 60).

The Child Protection Act includes a range of leading symptoms under the umbrella term of additional needs: children exhibiting severe psychological or severe dissociative symptoms or those using psychoactive substances may all fall into the category of additional needs. In practice, it can be challenging to determine what types of issues should be prioritised in an additional needs care children's home. For instance, the needs of a youth struggling with substance use differ significantly from those of a child with a psychiatric illness (Miklósi, 2015). Questions arise about how these young individuals influence each other, what group dynamic processes develop within the group, and whether these processes support or hinder therapeutic work.

Bede (et al. 2010) highlights that integrated care models are ineffective for adolescents, particularly those with additional needs, for individuals grappling with severe drug abuse or dependency, entirely different pedagogical and psychological tools are required compared to working with children dealing with behavioural disorders or conduct problems.

The special needs category also raises professional-methodological questions when defining the target group for special needs children's homes. Should the characteristics of the target group be narrowly defined to ensure specific care, or could this be counterproductive due to the risk of segregation?

The issue of segregation versus integration offers numerous dilemmas for discussion (Büki, 2009). Presenting the two concepts as opposites may suggest that institutions established for children with special, additional, or dual needs—where only those belonging to the given target group reside—represent societal exclusion rather than positive discrimination. However, such positive discrimination could enable enhanced support, personalised attention, tailored development to meet individual needs, and preparation for social integration for the affected individuals.

The question, therefore, is not (only) about which type of institution best facilitates the development of a child's potential but also about what further support can or should be provided to children's homes or foster parents caring for children with special and/or additional needs. Professional assistance is crucial to help children with special needs reach the highest possible level of self-sufficiency. However, the current care system is unable to provide this support with sufficient efficiency (Demcsik, 2015). According to the appendix of the NM Decree (Appendix 1: Staffing norms and minimum personnel requirements for child welfare and child protection services), only in additional needs care children's homes are required to have an extra educator or child supervisor per group. In contrast, the number of professional caregivers assigned to a group in special needs children's homes is the same as for children with standard needs, even though caring for children with multiple disabilities or chronic illnesses obviously entails more and different types of tasks for caregivers and educators than caring for healthy children. In all types of institutions, it would be justifiable to increase the number of professionals available and to ensure regular supervision and further training opportunities for them. Based on a survey conducted among institutional leaders, Rác (2022) concluded that child protection professionals have minimal opportunities for relief from their heavy workloads under the current challenging operating conditions. Among those working in specialised care, only 11.5% were satisfied, reporting that the child protection system provides adequate tools for their tasks and that burnout among professionals is not prevalent.

Conceptualisation challenges related to children with special and/or additional needs pose difficulties for research methodologies and have significant implications for various aspects of child protection practice.

For minors (despite the differing terminologies and lack of alignment between the Public Education Act and the Child Protection Act), expert opinions define their needs, which, in an optimal scenario, would allow them to receive the appropriate care in suitable placements. However, stability is not characteristic of their care. Csurgó and Rácz (2012), in their study of young adults with disabilities who aged out of the child protection system, found that these individuals often received care at multiple placements during their time in the system: they experienced stays at various institutions and with several foster parents before being returned to children's homes.

Changes following the expiration of the legally prescribed duration of care at a single placement can be particularly challenging for children with additional needs, as they must adapt to a new system and new rules. Frequent placement changes are a characteristic care feature for children with additional needs. At the same time, prolonged stays at a single placement—where they can only reside for a specified period—can create different challenges.

As children with special needs approach adulthood, changing care placements, the necessity of aftercare, and the availability of relevant services become significant challenges. For those ageing out of the child protection system, a graduated and flexible service structure—where the level of support is adjusted to the individual's current life circumstances—has not yet been developed (Rácz & Riegler, 2015).

Under Section 93 of the Child Protection Act, individuals can receive aftercare based on various eligibility criteria. Those awaiting admission to a residential social institution or unable to sustain themselves independently and who reached adulthood with special or additional needs may receive aftercare until the end of their 22nd year. Those pursuing secondary education can receive support until the end of their 24th year. In contrast, those enrolled in higher education or adult education can request support until the end of their 25th year. Upon request, young adults with a student or higher education status may have their care extended at the discretion of the service provider until the end of their educational relationship, but no later than their 30th year.

For mentally impaired or disabled residents, helping them understand and accept the changes associated with reaching adulthood and later preparing them to move out of their care placement represents a significant professional challenge. This is particularly relevant when these children have spent many years in a special needs children's home, which has essentially become their permanent home.

For mentally impaired minors who are unable to care for themselves and lack suitable family support, the appointment of a legal guardian can be a viable solution. The guardian would provide legal representation and manage the individual's affairs as they transition into adulthood. The process for establishing guardianship can be initiated by the child protection guardian when the minor reaches the age of 17. Challenges arise when neither guardianship is established, nor a suitable social care facility placement is secured by the time the individual reaches adulthood. In such cases, creative, tailored solutions must be devised to ensure these young adults receive the secure and appropriate placement they need. Statistical data indicates that aftercare may be provided in special needs children's homes for residents requiring special care. However, no equivalent aftercare options exist for young people with additional needs. This highlights the necessity of developing specialised aftercare services for these individuals (Miklósi, 2015).

The regulations and procedural guidelines concerning cases of unauthorised absences are available and accessible. A pertinent question arises as to whether it is necessary to include provisions in the regulations issued by the service providers that differ from those applicable to children with standard needs, explicitly addressing children with special and additional needs. Developing a methodological guide for preventing and managing cases of unauthorised absences could provide valuable support for professionals working directly with children.

The results of this study confirm previous research findings while highlighting further critical issues affecting the child welfare system and the safety of care provided to children. The research aligns with practical experience by drawing attention to areas within the child protection system that require solutions and by raising new research questions. The exploratory analysis of this issue also reinforces that forming an informed opinion about the child protection field requires more than openness, goodwill, and a willingness to help. Due to the complexity of the topic, professional knowledge is indispensable.

To provide care and development tailored to the individual needs of children with special, additional and/or dual care requirements, well-prepared, professional, and creative specialists are essential. These professionals must be capable of creating an emotionally secure environment for traumatised children facing severe problems and applying professional and legal solutions even in the most difficult situations. In addition to the functioning of multidisciplinary teams, it is crucial to realise genuine cooperation among the actors supporting the child (parents, guardians, service institutions belonging to the child protection system and public education) and to consider possible intervention methods. According to the subsidiarity principle, the levels of task performance and competence boundaries must also be considered. When creating the framework conditions, professional considerations must be implemented at the maintainer level and sectoral management level.

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